

Benzacridines

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The preparation of substituted 7-aminobenz/c/acridines as potential amoebicides has been reported by Elslager *et al*¹. and by Short *et al*². The present communication deals with the preparation of some substituted 7-aminobenz/c/acridines and 12-aminobenz/a/-acridines as potential amoebicides, which have been found to possess high activity *in vitro* against *E. histolytica*.

The compounds were prepared by the action of 7-chlorobenz/c/acridine and 12-chlorobenz/a/acridine on the appropriate amine in phenol and were isolated as salicylates; three compounds (No. 3, 5 and 11) could not be crystallised as salicylates and have been characterised as picrates.

General Method of Preparation.—7-Chlorobenz/c/acridine or 12-chlorobenz/a/acridine (0.005 M) was dissolved in freshly distilled phenol (10 ml) by heating on a steam bath and a slight excess of the appropriate amine added. The mixture was kept at 120° for 2 hours and then poured into excess aqueous alkali. The base separated as a sticky solid which was washed with water and dried: it was extracted with ether and the ether extract treated with a solution of salicylic acid in ether to precipitate the salicylate. It usually separated as a gum which solidified in a day; after filtering and washing with ether, it was crystallised from 90% ethanol. In the case of the compounds No. 2, 4, 10, and 12, the salicylates were dissolved in boiling ethanol and ether added to give a slight turbidity; on standing overnight the salicylates crystallised.

The picrates were prepared by precipitating from an ethanolic solution of the base and crystallised from ethanol-pyridine. The compounds are listed in Table I.

Method of Assay.—The *in vitro* tests were carried out against a virulent strain of *E. histolytica*, obtained from the Central Drug Research Institute, Lucknow, and maintained on the Böeck-Drbohlav medium with a mixed bacterial flora supplemented with a loopful of rice starch. The stock test medium was a sterilized standard Ringer's solution buffered to pH 7.4 with 0.2% of sodium hydrogen phosphate.

The test compound was dissolved in water on the boiling water bath and graded doses from 0.1 to 1.0 ml, sufficient to give a final concentration of 1:10,000 to 1:1000,000, were taken in sterilized test tubes; the volume in each tube was brought to 2.0 ml with sterilized distilled water and 2.5 ml of a mixture of Ringer's solution and horse serum (4:1 v/v) added to each. A control tube without the drug was also kept. A loopful of sterilized

1. Elslager *et al.*, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1957, **79**, 4699; 1959, **80**, 451.
2. Short *et al.*, *ibid.*, 1959, **80**, 223.

TABLE I

No.	Name of the compound.	Formula.	M.P.	%Carbon. Found.	%Carbon. Reqd.	%Hydrogen. Found.	%Hydrogen. Reqd.	Minimum effective conc.
1	12-(2'-Diethylaminoethyl)amino- benz/s/acridine-S	$C_{23}H_{33}N_3 \cdot 2C_7H_6O_3$	182°	71.76	71.73	6.32	5.98	1 : 100,000
2	12-(3'-Diethylaminopropyl)amino- benz/s/acridine-S	$C_{24}H_{37}N_3 \cdot 2C_7H_6O_3$	160°	71.01	72.04	0.42	6.16	1 : 80,000
3	12-(5'-Diethylaminoamyl)amino- benz/s/acridine-P	$C_{26}H_{31}N_3 \cdot 2C_6H_9N_3O_7$	100°	54.34	54.00	4.05	4.39	1 : 300,000
4	12-(3'-Piperidinopropyl)amino- benz/s/acridine-S	$C_{23}H_{37}N_3 \cdot 2.5C_7H_6O_3$	178°	71.71	71.43	6.10	5.88	1 : 100,000
5	12-(5'-Piperidinoamyl)amino- benz/s/acridine-P	$C_{27}H_{31}N_3 \cdot 2C_6H_9N_3O_7$	126°	54.94	54.73	4.51	4.33	1 : 000,000
6	7-(2'-Diethylaminoethyl)amino- benz/c/acridine-S	$C_{23}H_{33}N_3 \cdot 2C_7H_6O_3$	184°	71.80	71.73	5.90	5.99	1 : 300,000
7	7-(3'-Diethylaminopropyl)amino- benz/c/acridine-S	$C_{24}H_{37}N_3 \cdot 2C_7H_6O_3$	184°	71.80	72.04	5.82	6.10	1 : 000,000
8	7-(5'-Diethylaminoamyl)amino- benz/c/acridine-S	$C_{26}H_{31}N_3 \cdot 2C_7H_6O_3$	130°	72.44	72.62	0.04	6.51	1 : 000,000
9	7-(3'-Piperidinopropyl)amino- benz/c/acridine-S	$C_{25}H_{37}N_3 \cdot 2.5C_7H_6O_3$	170°	71.16	71.43	5.50	5.89	1 : 000,000
10	7-(5'-Piperidinoamyl)amino- benz/c/acridine-S	$C_{27}H_{31}N_3 \cdot 2C_7H_6O_3$	130°	72.70	73.11	6.25	6.30	1 : 300,000
11	N-(2-Hydroxyethyl)-N'-(benz/o/ acridin-7-yl) ethylenediamine	$C_{21}H_{21}ON_3 \cdot 3(C_6H_5N_3O_7 \cdot H_2O)$	200°	43.12	43.17	3.13	3.08	1 : 300,000
12	N-(2-Hydroxyethyl)-N'-(benz/s/ acridin-12-yl)ethylenediamine-S ^{HT}	$C_{21}H_{15}ON_3 \cdot 2C_7H_6O_3$	140°	69.83	66.10	5.03	5.44	1 : 600,000

S. Saksyala, T. Floran, C. ~~...~~ allylic acid. $C_6H_5N_3O_7$ picric acid.

rice starch was added to each tube followed by 0.5 ml of the inoculum collected by pooling the growth from a number of culture tubes. The test tubes were then incubated at 37° for 24 hours and examined for the presence of amoebae. The absence of amoebae was taken as the evidence of amoebacidal effect and the minimum dose required for the complete elimination of the amoebae was considered as the minimum effective dose. The results are recorded in Table I.

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